

Pressure dependence of thermal decomposition of ammonium nitrate oxidizer

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There is an increasing interest in research and development of ecofriendly solid propellant systems which can replace the existing ones in applications particularly where the rockets have to be fired in close proximity of the personnel and smokeless HCl-free burning is desired. Ammonium nitrate (AN) is receiving wide attention as a possible substitute for ammonium perchlorate oxidizer in view of the hazardous nature of other candidates like nitramines and non-availability of substances like ammonium dinitramide in requisite quantities besides the cost effectiveness. The phase transitions and initial endothermic decomposition of ammonium nitrate, however, pose problems in its application in composite solid rocket propellants. The influence of pressure on phase transitions, melting and thermal decomposition characteristics of AN is required to be systematically studied in order to have an insight in the combustion mechanism of AN containing propellants. Pressure differential scanning calorimetric (PDSC) studies have consequently been conducted on pure AN under ambient conditions and upto a maximum inert pressure of 68.03 atm. The shifts in the phase transition peaks, melting and decomposition temperatures with pressure have been studied. It has been observed that thermal decomposition of AN remains an endothermic process upto a pressure of 20.41 atm and thereafter becomes exothermic in nature. Phase transitions, melting and decomposition processes are found to be pressure sensitive and the associated peaks register a positive temperature shift bearing a relationship with crystal structure in two distinct pressure segments corresponding to endo- and exothermic decomposition.

The rocket propellants with reduced smoke and acceptable burning characteristics are automatically favored for use in high accelerating tactical missiles. They can serve as an improved camouflage on the battlefield and may facilitate superior guidance and control due to the higher transmission of their rocket plume compared to metallized ammonium perchlorate (AP) containing composite solid propellants.

An additional motivation for developing chlorine-free propellants is the necessity of employing low-hazard, low-observable smoke propellants which eliminate both primary smoke of metal oxide and secondary smoke of water aerosol condensed from the atmosphere by the exhaust plume. Since HCl serves as a nucleation site for water vapor, chlorine must either be eliminated from the propellant or scavenged from the exhaust product using nitramines HMX or RDX though they are relatively hazardous materials.

The search for new 'clean burning' propellants is engendered by the demand for smokeless and less sensitive propellants suiting the ecological requirements calling for HCl-free burning. The solution of this problem primarily requires replacing AP by a different oxidizer. Leaving aside substance, like ammonium dinitramide, which is not available in required amounts, suitable candidates can be found

amongst nitrates and nitramines. As using nitramines in large rocket motors would necessitate the use of expensive equipment to prevent hazards, nitrates and especially the ammonium nitrate (AN) has received renewed interest as a possible energetic oxidizer for use in solid rockets in near future. Besides its clean burning characteristics, AN is cheap, readily available, less hazardous than AP, less sensitive to friction and impact and compatible with high energy fuel binders.

The use of AN as a major propellant ingredient, however poses some serious technical problems that must be overcome. Among these the phase transitions under storage conditions, leading to significant volume changes, hygroscopicity, low-burning rate, lower enthalpy of combustion with typical binders, low performance compared to AP and its inability to burn aluminium efficiently are some vital challenges. Efforts are being made globally to overcome these undesirable features of AN to enable its use as a substitute for AP wherever possible.

In the present work an attempt has been made to study the thermal decomposition behavior of the oxidizer, AN at different pressure using a pressure differential scanning calorimeter (PDSC) with a view to understand the role of pressure in influencing the various physicochemical processes,

*Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

phase transitions, melting and decomposition characteristics.

Results and discussion

Previous thermal decomposition studies¹⁻¹³ on AN have shown that the process is quite complicated. The difference in the reactions taking place in the gas phase and condensed phase are difficult to ascertain under practical conditions. It is understood that the different reaction regime would contribute differently with variation in temperature and pressure. It is reported that the balance of reactions shifts from ionic to radical mode at higher temperature^{1,3} and the reaction rate is affected by the gases enveloping the sample⁴. It is interesting to note that the surface temperature of burning AN remains in the range of 300–350^{14,15}. The slow decomposition behavior of AN in this temperature range of practical importance from propellant combustion view point has not been studied systematically under high pressure conditions. Such thermal response data are likely to be of immense utility in understanding the condensed phase and initial combustion mechanism of AN based propellants.

The DSC thermogram of pure AN at ambient pressure has been shown in Fig. 1. The thermogram clearly shows three transition peaks with temperatures of the order of 43.47,

Fig. 1. Thermogram showing phase transition, melting and decomposition of AN at ambient pressure.

92.08 and 130.70°. Ammonium nitrate is known to have six crystalline phases^{9,10}, however, two of them are noticeable only at subambient temperatures. The remaining phases are reported¹² to exhibit transitions between preceding stage temperatures and 32°, 84°, 125° and melt stage. These results have been obtained during heating of AN containing more than 0.1% moisture. Further, it has also been reported^{16,17} that different transition paths are observed during heating and cooling of AN depending upon moisture content and temperature. Our findings on pure AN crystals at ambient pressure (Table 1, serial No. 1) reveal that phase IV → III transition, converting orthorhombic to disordered orthorhombic form takes place at 43.47° and III → II tran-

Table 1. Effect of pressure on phase transition, melting and decomposition temperature of AN

Sl. no.	Pressure atm	Peak temperature (°C) for				
		Phase Transition			Melting	Decomposition
		IV → III	III → II	II → I		
1.	1	43.47	92.08	130.70	168.89	292.54
2.	13.61	42.05	93.50	129.37	170.19	311.40
3.	20.41	39.14	93.21	129.09	170.48	320.13
4.	27.21	46.73	94.51	130.65	172.50	312.33
5.	40.82	50.01	92.39	133.26	175.75	310.66
6.	54.42	51.17	90.16	134.56	175.33	311.15
7.	68.03	45.44	90.86	131.16	157.54	313.55

sition from disordered orthorhombic form to tetragonal crystalline stage effects at 92.08°. Further, phase II → I transition, transforming tetragonal to cubic crystal form appears at 130.70°. The comparison of results obtained in the present work with that reported in literature¹² shows the positive shifts of 11.47, 8.08 and 5.70° in the peak temperatures of aforesaid transitions chronologically although the melting peak temperature (168.89°) is in excellent agreement with the reported^{6,18} value. These results have been obtained on extra pure AN crystals with an average particle size of 200 μm and nearly constant sample size using state of art equipment with unparalleled sensitivity. The departure from reported values in literature may be due to sample size and history^{19,20}, crucible type¹⁹, accuracy of the employed measuring device, moisture¹¹ and/or impurity content as well as sample heating rate. One or more of these factors may be operative in affecting the transition temperature shifts. This gets further support from the report that even about 0.1% change in moisture content in dry AN sample may cause the disappearance or appearance of polymorphic change (viz. III → II) in the DSC thermogram¹². The sample heating rates are also observed to be of importance in influencing the shifts in transition peak temperatures. The results obtained in the present study at a heating rate of 10°/min, compared to that reported in literature¹¹ at a heating of 2°/min using the similar equipment reveal that the peak temperatures corresponding to transformations IV → III and III → II are heating rate sensitive, whereas, II → I is not. It may, further be noted that the first transition registered a positive temperature shifts with heating rate while second shows the reverse trend. This is supported by the results reported elsewhere on energy of crystal transformations¹⁹.

The melting peak is seen to appear at 168.89° after the completion of the polymorphic transitions. Thereafter, the decomposition of AN is seen to start from 207.77° to peak out at 292.54° which goes on to completion around 300°. It

may be noticed that all the processes phase transitions, melting and decomposition are endothermic in nature. The energies associated with various polymorphic transitions and melting of AN, reported elsewhere¹⁹ show considerable divergence in their magnitudes. An attempt has, therefore, been made to compute the associated enthalpy values accurately using Area Standard Programme (PL-ETA). The results have been presented in Table 2, sl. no. 1, as a function of pressure.

The entire endothermic process is found to be accompa-

Table 2. Pressure dependence of energy associated with phase transition, melting and thermal decomposition of AN

Sl. no.	Pressure atm	Associated heat (Cal/g) for				
		Phase Transition			Melting	Decomposition
		IV → III	III → II	II → I		
1.	1	-4.60	-3.90	-11.83	-13.35	-323.21
2.	13.61	-2.15	-2.41	-05.80	-08.10	-41.72
3.	20.41	-2.26	-2.26	-06.67	-09.45	-06.37
4.	27.21	-1.23	-2.26	-06.95	-9.88	16.03
5.	40.82	-4.41	-4.55	-14.54	-18.16	108.49
6.	54.42	-0.26	-0.63	-0.44	0.68	42.64
7.	68.03	-1.15	-1.06	-03.06	-02.30	49.73

nied with the absorption of 356.89 cal/g of heat at ambient pressure. Considering the extreme endothermicity of the oxidant, AN, when used in composite solid propellants with endothermic binders, which is generally the case, one can apprehend poor ignitability and combustion at least under ambient conditions. However, the utility of such data seems to be limited in the light of high pressure and temperature encountered in combustion chamber of rocket engines. As a consequence, efforts have been made to study the effect of pressure on the thermal behavior of AN.

The results on the effect of pressure on phase transition, melting and decomposition of AN have been presented in Figs. 2–7 and summarized in Table 1 in the pressure range of ambient to 68.03 atm. A close look at the data clearly reveals the following facts. (a) There are two clearcut regions – one endothermic upto a pressure of approximately 21 atm and the other exothermic beyond it as far as the effect of pressure on various processes is concerned. To be more precise, the change from endo- to exothermic region takes place around 21.41 atm as obtained graphically from a plot of heat of decomposition versus pressure. (b) The peaks corresponding to phase transitions IV → III and II → I shift to lower temperature side in the endothermic zone while the reverse trend is observed in the exothermic zone (shift to higher temperature side). (c) The transition from

Fig. 2. A DSC scan of AN at 13.61 atm.

phase III → II, however, shows positive shift in the peak temperature in endothermic zone and generally negative shift in the exothermic zone. (d) Melting peak, in general, shifts always to higher temperature side with rise in pressure, except a sudden drop observed at 68.03 atm. This appears to be quite surprising. Repeated experiments at this pressure, however, have shown a melting point range from 157.54 to

Fig. 3. Thermograms of AN at 20.41 atm.

167.68°, possibly due to enormously increased instability in DSC thermogram (not shown) at high pressure. (e) The decomposition peak temperature, however, shows an increasing trend in the endothermic region but registers a decrease-

Fig. 4. DSC thermograms of AN at 27.21 atm

Fig. 5. DSC thermograms of AN at 40.82 atm.

ing tendency in the exothermic zone with pressure.

The shifting of peaks corresponding to transitions IV → III and II → I in endothermic zone can be understood only in the light of change in specific volume of AN crystals. It is reported that in the simplest case like this, all atomic coordinates and bond lengths simply scale with the lattice parameter, i.e. the relative coordinates would remain constant²¹. It appears that increase in volume takes place in the pres-

Fig. 6. DSC thermograms of AN at 54.42 atm.

sure range of 1–21.5 atm, suggesting that role played by temperature is too significant to outway the effect of pressure. Beyond this limit, i.e. in the exothermic region, the opposite trend seems to be valid probably due to reversal of above trend under high pressure forging effect following Le

Fig. 7. DSC thermograms of AN at 68.03 atm.

Chatelier's principle. This also seems to take care of transition III → II which follows more or less reverse trend. The exhibition of positive shift (higher temperature side) in melting peak temperature with pressure can also be attributed to increase in density of molten AN in comparison to solid crystals.

This can be substantiated if specific volume (cm^3/g) of different phases at least under phase transition condition at a given pressure can be computed. An effort has been done to get such a data by theoretically calculating the densities of different crystalline phases using unit cell parameters reported by Hermann and Engel¹¹ with the help of equation²²,

$$\rho = nM/(A_N V) \quad (1)$$

where n , M , A_N and V denote the number of particles (molecules/atoms/ions) in the unit cells, molar mass, Avogadro number and the volume of unit cell of a given phase computed from lattice parameters (recorded in Table 3), respectively. The specific volumes obtained by taking reciprocals of the respective ρ -values at corresponding temperature have also been reported in Table 3 (column-3). It may, however, be mentioned that the specific volumes reported therein are expected to be slightly more as the temperatures involved in the present study are on the higher side than the reported ones.

Table 3. Computed specific volume of phases at different temperatures

Phase	Volume of unit cell ($\times 10^{-23} \text{ cm}^3$)	Sp. vol. cm^3/g	Measured temp. ($^\circ\text{C}$)
IV	15.4394	0.5792	22
III	32.3108	0.6080	45
II	16.1347	0.6070	82
I	8.3224	0.6262	150

It is clearly seen (Table 3) that IV → III and II → I phase transitions are accompanied with increase in volume, whereas III → II transformation with marginal decrease. As the transition and associated peak temperatures encountered in the present study are different, attempts have been made to compute at least change in specific volume accompanied with phase transformation using Clapeyron-Claius equation,

$$\frac{dT}{dP} = \frac{T(V_i - V_f)}{\Delta H} \quad (2)$$

where, dT/dP , T , ΔH , V_i and V_f stand for change in temperature per unit change in pressure (K per atm), absolute peak

temperature (°C), energy change associated with transition peak (cal/g), and specific volume of the initial and final phase involved in crystal transformations process, respectively. The computed results on specific volume change during phase transition process have been reported in Table 4 as a function of pressure. A close look at the results clearly indicates that in the endothermic region the specific volumes of phases III (disordered octahedral) and I (cubic) are higher than phases IV (octahedral) and II (tetragonal), respectively. However, beyond endothermic region the reverse trend is

Table 4. Effect of pressure on specific volume change during phase transition of AN

Sl. no.	ΔP (atm)	Sp. vol. change ($V_i - V_f$) ($\times 10^{-2}$ cm ³ /g) during phases transition		
		IV \rightarrow III	III \rightarrow II	II \rightarrow I
1.	12.61	-23.775	11.985	-19.526
2.	19.41	-53.189	5.829	-17.697
3.	26.21	13.519	9.155	-0.419
4.	39.82	60.627	1.583	28.965
5.	53.42	3.034	-1.037	1.322
6.	67.03	2.727	-0.877	0.661

followed, i.e. in the exothermic region the specific volumes of phases III and I are significantly decreased from their counter crystal structures. In the case of phase transition of disordered octahedral to tetragonal (III \rightarrow II) the reverse trend is observed. This corroborates our speculation made earlier. This gets further support from current general conviction that pressure may affect critical (peak) temperature in an intrinsic way, mainly due to lattice rearrangement induced by pressure^{23,24}. As a result, all atomic coordinates and bond lengths simply scale with the lattice parameters, however, the relative atomic coordinates remain constant²¹.

The positive shift, in general, of decomposition peak with pressure (Table 1, column-7) in comparison to ambient condition is understandable because the net result of condensed phase as well as gas phase decomposition reactions shifts to exothermic domain. A comparison of decomposition peak data with its onset temperature recorded in Table 5 (column-3) leads to suggest that in the endothermic region at relatively low pressures (1 and 13.61 atm) perhaps condensed phase/surface reactions are predominant as the heat energy flows from heat source to sample (Figs. 1 and 2). Further, it is also apparent that the reactions are significantly slow as it takes considerable time to reach to partial or total completion. However, at or around the endo- to exo-transition point (at 20.41 atm pressure), the onset temperature (311.84°) of decomposition peaks out at 320.13°. It

Table 5. Effect of pressure on onset decomposition temperature of ammonium nitrate

Sl. no.	Press. atm	Decomp. onset temp. (°C)
1.	1	208.56
2.	13.61	214.29
3.	20.41	311.84
4.	27.21	268.54
5.	40.82	259.10
6.	54.42	273.31
7.	68.03	310.15

may be apprehended that at this stage gas phase exothermic reactions between primary decomposition products – NH₃ and HNO₃ come into play. This trend is seen to be followed even at higher pressures. It may also be argued that AN decomposition is insensitive to pressure as the peak decomposition temperatures (barring the one observed at 20.41 atm) lie between 310.66 and 13.55° in a narrow range.

The kinetic parameters like energy of activation and pre-exponential factor in the temperature range of ambient to 350° under inert pressure of 1 atm to 20.41 atm have been found to lie between 27.65 and 33.91 kcal mol⁻¹ and 11.38 and 14.31, respectively.

Experimental

The experimental studies have been carried out with a view to understand the thermal decomposition behavior of the eco-friendly oxidizer, AN (E. Merck). The oxidizer was used after drying at 110° for 3–4 h followed by micro-pulverization under controlled RH of 45%. An average particle size of 200 μ m was selected for the study.

A heat flux type PDSC (polymer Laboratory, UK) was used for conducting differential scanning calorimetric studies. About 8–10 mg of AN sample was taken in an aluminium crucible (2 mm high, 60 μ l-internal volume) and placed in the circular well meant for the sample crucible. The reference crucible was also positioned in its place. Water was circulated through the cooling jacket and the flow of dry N₂ gas (25 ml/min) was maintained throughout the run. The temperature range was set from ambient to 350° in each case at a heating rate of 10°/min. The heat flow rate was recorded as a function of temperature by data acquisition system operated with the help of an acquire subroutine program included in the main software plus V, version 5.2 of the DSC system. The acquired data were analyzed using a CRT plot program and necessary software supplied by the manufacturer.

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